

11 Hard Questions– 11 Simple Answers – 8 Theory

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The paper is meant of a brief overview of the entire ambit of the new theory and the enigmas to which it was able to shade light upon. There is no elaboration on how the equations were derived nor their meaning.

Introduction

1. What is the dark energy?

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

2. Why there are only three families?

There should be a fourth family below first generation. Mass is an arbitrary variation of the manifold converging inward, associated with a symmetry break of the form: $8 - (1)$.

3. What is dark matter? The additional families whose mass is converging to zero below first generation.

4. Why there are only four forces in nature?

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.2)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.3)$$

5. Why does nature generate force in the first place?

Force is a net curvature on the manifold. Net curvature may accrue. There is no reason behind it. We can describe it in the coupling constants primordial function.

6. Why is the universe flat?

Arbitrary amount of curvature must vanish. The universe is part of an infinite multiverse packet.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

7. Why is the universe not completely isotropic?

Arbitrary amount of curvature vanish into matter.

8. How does the arrow of time arise?

$$\overrightarrow{\hspace{10em}}$$

$$1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots$$

9. Why does the arrow one sided?

Each interaction is weaker than its preceding; the net curvature is a smaller and smaller portion of the whole cluster of variation. Going the opposite side is synonymous with going from lower state of energy to a higher state, i.e. against rules of thermodynamics.

10. Can physics be unified?

It is impossible to unify infinite series of bosonic fields and families. The only thing that can be unified is ideas.

11. Is god playing with dices?

No. he is playing a Russian roulette, and each number on the roulette is prime or one. Nature is random and chaotic.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)